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ANALYSIS OF SOME ASPECTS OF THE GREENHOUSE EFFECT IN THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

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Annotation: Using the information data of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus, data on changes in the average annual air temperature in the Republic of Belarus as an indicator of the greenhouse effect were studied and analyzed, its direct relationship with changes in the amount of waste, passenger turnover, the area of forest funds, forest fires was revealed. Analysis of the dynamics of the average annual temperature showed that the greenhouse effect would continue to develop in the near future.

Keywords: greenhouse effect, average annual air temperature

АНАЛИЗ НЕКОТОРЫХ АСПЕКТОВ ПАРНИКОВОГО ЭФФЕКТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ БЕЛАРУСЬ

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Аннотация: Используя информационные данные Национального статистического комитета Республики Беларусь, изучены и проанализированы данные об изменении среднегодовой температуры воздуха в Республике Беларусь, как индикаторного показателя парникового эффекта, выявлена его прямая взаимосвязь с изменением количества отходов, пассажирооборота, площади лесных фондов, лесных пожаров. Анализ

динамики среднегодовой температуры показал, что парниковый эффект в течение короткого времени будет развиваться и дальше.

Ключевые слова: парниковый эффект, среднегодовая температура воздуха

Relevance. The global problem of our time is the greenhouse effect. The greenhouse effect is an increase in the temperature of the earth's surface due to the concentration of greenhouse gases and the heating of the lower layers of the atmosphere. It is known that significant parts of the infrared rays of the solar spectrum passing through the atmosphere are reflected from the Earth's surface. Due to the large wavelength, the reflected radiation is partially absorbed by nitrogen dioxide and tropospheric ozone, the other part is re-reflected to the Earth. Due to this circumstance, the Earth's surface is even more heated. This phenomenon is called the greenhouse effect. The greatest contribution to the described effect is made by carbon dioxide (CO₂). Now, the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere is 275 ppmv (0.34 %). It increases by about 1.6 ppmv, or 0.5 % per year. Over the XX century, the concentration of CO₂ increased by 20 %.

Methane (CH₄) is formed as a result of the vital activity of anaerobic microorganisms. Its main sources are tundra, wetlands, termite mounds, extraction and use of natural gas, combustion of biological masses, and the coal industry [1, 5]. In 1985, the average concentration of methane in the atmosphere was 1.7 ppmv in the north and 16 ppmv in the southern hemisphere. Its annual content in the air increases by about 1 %.

The global concentration of nitrogen dioxide in 1985 averaged 310 ppbv with small geographic errors. The period of presence in the atmosphere is 150 years. The annual growth rate is 0.2-0.3 %. The main natural source of nitrogen dioxide is the processes of nitrification in the soil. Anthropogenic origin is associated with the use of nitrogen fertilizers and fuel combustion.

Tropospheric ozone also contributes to the greenhouse effect. An increase in tropospheric ozone concentration of 50 % is predicted to be accompanied by an increase in temperature of approximately 0.3 °C [2].

The reasons for the greenhouse effect are [1]:

- ingress of industrial gases into the atmosphere;
- decomposition and burning of garbage at landfills, which contributes to an increase in greenhouse gases;
- car exhaust gases that pollute the air and increase the greenhouse effect;
- use in industry of combustible minerals (natural gas, oil, coal), when burned, a considerable amount of carbon dioxide and other harmful compounds is emitted into the atmosphere;

- fertilization of lands containing various amounts of compounds, as a result of the evaporation of which nitrogen is released – one of the greenhouse gases;
- deforestation, which are capable of absorbing carbon dioxide and emitting oxygen, and with the destruction of every tree on the planet, the amount of CO₂ in the air increases;
- forest fires are one of the sources of destruction of vegetation on the planet;
- an increase in the population affects an increase in the demand for food, clothing, housing, and to ensure this, industrial production is growing, which is increasingly polluting the air with greenhouse gases.

Possible consequences of the greenhouse effect [3, 6]:

- shift in the intensity and frequency of precipitation;
- rise in ocean level;
- threat to biodiversity and ecosystems;
- climate change;
- melting of glaciers;
- decline in agricultural productivity;
- shortage of drinking water;
- increased risks of complications of human health.

Purpose. To study and analyze data on changes in the average annual air temperature in the Republic of Belarus, as an indicator of the greenhouse effect, to reveal its relationship with changes in the amount of waste, passenger traffic, area of forest resources, forest fires, using the information data of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus [4].

Materials and methods of a research. Search and analysis of scientific and practical information over the past 10 years (from 2010 to 2019) on the following issues: average annual air temperature in the Republic of Belarus; waste generation; passenger turnover in the country; forest area in the Republic of Belarus; areas of forest fires (in 2012-2018); received on the Internet site on the website of the National Statistical Committee of the Republic of Belarus [4].

Results and discussion. It was found that the average annual air temperature in the Republic of Belarus in 2010-2019. increased by 1.9 °C (from 6.9 °C to 8.8 °C), which is significant for a period of 10 years.

It is shown that the production waste generation in the Republic of Belarus increased by 17062 thousand tons in 2010-2019 (43775 thousand tons in 2010 to 60837 thousand tons in 2019). Production waste includes waste generated in the course of economic activity (production of products, energy, performance of works, and provision of services), by-products and related products of mining and processing of minerals. Landfills emit methane gas.

The total passenger turnover in the country increased by 4075.9 passengers/km (from 23498.2 passengers/km in 2010 to 27574.1 passengers/km in 2019). The total passenger turnover includes all types of transport (road, rail, inland waterway, air transport and metro) per capita of the country. Modern vehicles emit into the atmosphere: carbon monoxide, nitrogen and sulfur oxides, hydrocarbons, soot, etc., which directly affects the formation of the greenhouse effect.

The total area of the forest fund in the country increased by 2.34 thousand km² (from 80.46 thousand km² in 2010 to 82.8 thousand km² in 2019). The structure of the forest fund includes: 1) forests located on the lands of the forest fund and lands of other categories, and the lands covered by them; 2) forest land, not covered with forests, and non-forest land, located within the boundaries of forestlands and lands of other categories provided for forestry. Forests prevent the rapid formation of the greenhouse effect, and the fact that the area of forests has increased is only a positive moment, since forests absorb CO₂ and release O₂.

Forest fires in 2012-2018 occurred less frequently (by 50 cases per year), but the area affected by fires increased by 1,060 hectares (from 189 hectares in 2012 to 1249 hectares in 2018), which accelerates the greenhouse effect not only due to a decrease in the number of trees which convert CO₂ and release O₂, but due to the very fact of combustion, at which CO₂ is released into the atmosphere.

Conclusions. Analysis of the dynamics of the average annual temperature indicates that the greenhouse effect will rapidly develop in the near future, since there is a significant change in the amount of waste, passenger traffic, and the area of forest fires.

To slow down the greenhouse effect, it is necessary:

- to reduce the amount of waste by introducing reusable containers;
- widely use alternative energy and introduce energy-saving technologies;
- to develop new environmentally friendly and low-carbon technologies;
- fight forest fires and restore forests, which are natural absorbers of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

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[3] The greenhouse effect is the rise in temperature on the planet's surface as a result of thermal energy that appears in the atmosphere due to the heating of gases. The main gases that lead to the greenhouse effect on Earth are water vapor

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